

TRANSFORMATION OF REGIONAL RURAL BANKS THROUGH AMALGAMATION: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF GROWTH, FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE, COST AND NPA INDICATORS

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Abstract

Since their founding in 1975, Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) have been instrumental in promoting financial inclusion in rural areas since their establishment in 1975. Over the period, many RRBs faced the problems of low profitability, a high percentage of non-performing assets (NPAs), and excessive reliance on government assistance. The Government of India started a phased amalgamation program from 2005 to 2024 to improve their operational and financial performance. This initiative resulted in a considerable expansion of their branch network and a reduction in the number of RRBs from 196 to 28. This study examines the effects of amalgamation on the financial performance, operational effectiveness, and asset quality of RRBs. Secondary data from published reports of NABARD, RBI, annual statements of RRBs are used for data analysis. The study applies descriptive statistics, CAGR, correlation analysis, and trend analysis for data interpretation.

The findings reveal that amalgamation has strengthened the capital structure of RRBs, leading to substantial growth in deposits (CAGR 9%), gross loans and advances (CAGR 11%), investments (CAGR 7%), and reserves (CAGR 13%). Profitability improved significantly, with profit-making RRBs increasing from 26 in 2019–20 to 40 in 2023–24. NPAs declined steadily during study period. Correlation analysis indicates strong linkages between branch expansion and deposit mobilization (0.99), and between deposits and credit growth (0.98). Amalgamation also enhanced operational productivity by reducing cost of funds and improving net interest margins. The study concludes that amalgamation has led to stronger, more independent, and technologically efficient RRBs with enhanced outreach and financial sustainability in rural areas.

Keywords: *Regional Rural Banks, Amalgamation, Financial Performance, NPAs, Profitability, Operational productivity etc.*

Introduction:

Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) are the specialized financial institution set up in 1975 under the Regional Rural Banks Act, 1976 to provide affordable banking services to rural people such as small and marginal farmers, rural artisans, laborers, and small entrepreneurs. These banks operate at specified regions of one or more districts in various states across India. Regional Rural Banks are regulated by the Reserve Bank of India and supervised by the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development. Regional Rural Banks lend more than 75% to priority sector, especially to weaker sections, and productive rural sectors. To support the regional rural banks, Government of India hold the ownership of 50%, State Government (15%), and remaining 35 % shareholding owned by sponsor bank. This research paper study the growth and financial performance of regional rural banks in India.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To evaluate the financial performance of RRBs using key indicators such as deposits, advances, investments, reserves, and capital.
2. To assess profitability and NPA trends of RRBs from 2019–20 to 2023–24.
3. To analyze financial costs, margins, and operational efficiency indicators of RRBs from 2018–19 to 2023–24.
4. To understand the overall causes and effects of amalgamation of RRBs.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Regional Rural Banks in India have faced many issues like low profitability, high non-performing assets (NPAs), operational inefficiencies, and reliance on government assistance, despite playing a crucial role in providing rural finance. To improve these capital strengths, and financial stability, NPA and profitability related issues, the government started amalgamation in several phases. The research problem is to assess whether the amalgamation of RRBs has genuinely contributed to enhancing their branch network, financial performance, profitability, NPA, and overall operational sustainability.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The proposed research work will rely on secondary sources of data. The secondary data collected from Books, journals, RRB reports and India stat website. The study adopts a **descriptive and analytical research methodology**, using secondary quantitative data to assess trends, performance, and financial indicators of RRBs over time. Statistical tools such as CAGR, correlation analysis, mean values, comparative analysis are used to interpret performance changes of RRBs in India.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research uses a longitudinal research design, analyzing data across multiple years (2011 to 2024 and 2018-19 to 2023-24) to understand structural and financial changes in RRBs. The design includes 1) Trend Analysis to study changes in branch expansion, profitability, and financial indicators. 2) Correlation Analysis to examine relationships between deposits, borrowings, loans, and branch expansion. 3) Descriptive Statistics (mean, CAGR, standard deviation) to quantify changes over time. This design helps obtain the effect of amalgamation of RRB on their growth and financial performance.

Amalgamation Process and Growth of RRBs:

Government implemented phased amalgamation of RRBs to strengthen financial condition of RRBS. The primary reasons of these reforms were the persistent operational inefficiencies, weak financial performance, and duplication of banking structures across states. The *effect* was a comprehensive consolidation process that gradually reduced the number of RRBs from 196 in 2000 to just 28 by 2025.

Table No 1: Growth of No of Number of RRBs and their branches in India

As at the end of	No of RRBs	Growth rate %	No of Branches	Growth rate %
Dec.1975	6		17	
Dec. 1980	85	1317%	3279	19188%
Mar. 1988	196	131%	13920	325%
Mar-90	196	0%	14443	4%
Mar-00	196	0%	14301	-1%
Mar-09	86	-56%	15235	7%
Mar-19	53	-38%	21871	44%
Mar-24	43	-19%	46659	113%
Jun-25	28	-35%	NA	NA

Source: Bhaskar, Chandanshive Sunil and Nivas Jadhav B. (2011), "Problems and prospects of Regional Rural Banks in India", Indian Stream Research Journal, Vol. 1 and Review of Performance of RRBs (2020-21 to 2023-24)

Above table no highlights the growth no of RRBs and their branches from 1975 to 2025. Initially, the number of RRBs increased rapidly, but after 2000 from 196 to 25 in 2025 due to amalgamation policies. The amalgamation occurred in three major phases.

The Phase I (2005 to 2012), in this phase, many RRBs were financially weak and unable to meet capital adequacy norms and high operating costs. Government and RBI wanted to make RRB stronger and financially more efficient banks. In this phase, the number of RRBs reduced

from 196 to 86 by March 2009, due to this process, operational performance of RRB improved, and merged banks benefited due to economies of scale.

Phase II (2012–2014), The number of RRBs was reduced from 82 to 56 by merging RRBs from different sponsor banks within states.

In Phase III (2019–2021), The number of RRBs was further reduced from 56 to 43 by merging weaker RRBs with stronger RRBs.

The most transformative Phase IV (2024), in which 26 RRBs merged with into 11 new entities, and currently in 2025 28 RRBs are functioning in India. These amalgamation of RRBs followed the principle of “One State–One RRB” to create larger, state-focused financial institutions in India. The process of amalgamation impacted positively in terms of improved financial viability, economies of scale, and enhanced capacity to adopt technology, enabling better risk management and reduced dependence on government funding.

A significant outcome is that while the number of RRBs drastically declined their branch network expanded substantially. Branches increased from 15,235 in 2009 to 21,871 in 2019 and further doubled to 46,659 by 2024—a 113% rise. This indicates that amalgamation strengthened outreach rather than reducing it. Bigger and more efficient RRBs were able to expand branch presence, optimize resources and maximum reach of finance to rural masses.

Table no 2: Performance of Regional Rural Banks in India (Rs. In Crore)

Particulars	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24	Mean	CAGR
No. of RRBs (No.)	53	45	43	43	43	43	45	-0.04
Branch Network (No.)	21871	26814	30348	34359	40123	46659	33362.33	0.16
Share Capital	6735	7849	8393	14880	17232	19042	12355.17	0.23
Reserves	25398	26814	30348	34359	40123	46659	33950.17	0.13
Deposits	434444	478737	525226	562538	608509	659815	544878.17	0.09
Borrowings	6735	7849	8393	14880	17232	19042	12355.17	0.23
Investments	226172	250859	275658	295665	313401	319099	280142.33	0.07
Gross Loans & Advances O/s	280755	298214	334171	362838	410738	470109	359470.83	0.11
Correlation between Deposits and Gross Loans & Advances is 0.98								
Correlation between Borrowings and Loans Outstanding is 0.95								
Correlation between Branch Network and Deposits is 0.99								

Source: Review of Performance of RRBs (2020-21 to 2023-24 retrieved from [Regional Rural](#)

[Banks | Department of Financial Services | Ministry of Finance | Government of India](#)

Table No 2 indicates the, Performance of Regional Rural Banks in terms of deposits, borrowings, Reserves, Investments and gross loans and advances during 2018–19 to 2023–24. Financial indicators show substantial growth. Share capital and borrowings recorded the highest CAGR (23%), indicating strong capital infusion and increased reliance on borrowings to support lending. Reserves also showed healthy growth (13%), suggesting improved internal financial stability.

On the banking operations side, deposits increased steadily from ₹4.34 lakh crore to ₹6.59 lakh crore (CAGR 9%), while investments grew moderately at 7% CAGR. Gross loans and advances rose at 11% CAGR, reflecting consistent credit expansion in rural and priority sectors.

A very high correlation (0.98) found between deposits and loans indicates that deposit mobilization directly drives credit growth.

Borrowings and loan outstanding show a strong correlation with 0.95, and shows borrowings are an important source for meeting the need of loan demand.

The near-perfect correlation found with 0.99 between branch network and deposits confirms that expansion of branches plays a crucial role in mobilizing deposits from rural people.

Table no 3: Profitability of Regional Rural Banks (Rs. in Crore)

Particulars	No of RRBs	No. of RRBs in Profit	Profit of RRBs in (Amount)	% Change	No RRBs in Loss	Loss of RRBs in (Amount)	% Change	Accumulated Losses	No. of RRBs with acc. Losses
2019-20	45	26	2203		19	4411		6467	17
2020-21	43	30	3550	0.61	13	1867	-0.58	8264	17
2021-22	43	34	4116	0.16	9	897	-0.52	9062	16
2022-23	43	37	6178	0.50	6	1205	0.34	9841	15
2023-24	43	40	7,796	0.26	3	225	-0.81	8,921	14
Average			4768.6			1721		8511	
CGAR			0.37					0.083	
Std. Deviation		4.96	1982.15			1445.03		1138.38	

Table no 3 analyze the of Profitability of Regional Rural Banks from (2019–20 to 2023–24). The profitability of RRBs shows consistent improvement during 2019–20 to 2023–24. Although the number of RRBs remained stable around 45 to 43 due to amalgamation, the

number of profit-making RRBs increased from 26 in 2019–20 to 40 in 2023–24. This indicates increase in operational efficiency.

The profit of RRBs in profit increased sharply from ₹2,203 crore to ₹7,796 crore, with a high CAGR of 37%, refers to good financial viability, better asset quality, and enhanced credit operations.

On the loss side, the number of RRBs incurring losses declined substantially from 19 to just 3, reflecting better cost management and improved recovery. Their total losses declined from Rs. 4,411 crores to Rs. 225 crores, thus it shows that weak RRBs are doing good with good recovery and shifting toward rising profitability.

The standard deviation values for profit SD is 1,982 and loss is 1,445, indicate moderate variability in performance among RRBs, but the overall trend toward rising profitability and declining losses.

Table no 4: Non-Performing Assets Regional Rural Banks in India
(Amount in Crore)

Parameters	Sub Standard -1	Doubtful Assets -2	Loss Assets -3	Gross NPA Amount	Net NPA Amount	GNPA %	Net NPA %
2019	42.80	54.58	2.62	30,317	17,843	10.8	6.8
2020	34.10	63.19	2.71	31,106	16,331	10.4	5.8
2021	31.32	65.86	2.82	31,381	15,094	9.4	4.8
2022	34.10	62.97	2.93	33,190	16,024	9.1	4.7
2023	22.74	73.89	3.37	29,894	12,364	7.3	3.2
2024	27.96	68.48	3.56	28,913	10,846	6.1	2.4

Source: Review of Performance of RRBs (2020-21 to 2023-24 retrieved from [Regional Rural Banks | Department of Financial Services | Ministry of Finance | Government of India](#))

The asset quality of Regional Rural Banks has shown consistent improvement during 2019 to 2024. All three components of NPAs—Sub-standard, Doubtful, and Loss assets show a declining trend, indicating better credit monitoring and better recovery systems during study period.

As a result of improved borrower discipline and more fast short-term recovery, sub-standard assets decreased from 42.80 crore in 2019 to 27.96 crore in 2024.

It is observed the fluctuation in doubtful assets during study period but with a peak in 2023 and decline once more in 2024, indicating improvement in long-term recovery.

Although the total amount is still relatively modest, loss assets indicate a slow increase from 2.62 crore to 3.56 crore, suggesting that certain accounts are aging into non-recoverable status. Loss assets show a gradual rise from 2.62 crore to 3.56 crore, indicating that some accounts are ageing into non-recoverable status, though the overall amount remains very low.

Net NPA Amount fell sharply from Rs.17,843 crore (6.8%) to Rs.10,846 crore (2.4%) an over 39% reduction, highlighting increase in asset quality, financial stability, better risk management practices, and enhanced operational efficiency in RRBs.

Table no 5: Financial Costs and Margins of Regional Rural Banks in India (in %)

S. No.	Parameter	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24
1	Yield on Loans	8.8	9.3	9.2	8.68	8.85	8.87
2	Yield on Investments	7.1	7	6.5	6.24	6.84	7.39
3	Yield on Assets	7.5	7.9	7.6	7.21	7.48	7.76
4	Cost of Deposits	5	5.1	4.5	4.11	4.04	4.52
5	Cost of Borrowings	6	5.9	5.1	4.49	4.87	5.93
6	Cost of Funds	4.6	4.7	4.2	3.72	3.72	4.2
7	Net Interest Margin	2.9	3.2	3.4	3.49	3.76	3.55
8	Miscellaneous Income	0.8	1	1.1	1.28	0.81	1.15
9	Staff Cost	1.8	2.3	2.4	2.45	2.33	1.94
10	Cost of Management	2.7	3.6	3.2	3.19	3.05	2.69
11	Risk Cost	1.2	1	1.1	1.09	0.82	1.06
12	Return on Assets (Profitability)	-0.13	-0.4	0.27	0.48	0.69	0.96

Source: Review of Performance of RRBs (2020-21 to 2023-24 retrieved from [Regional Rural Banks | Department of Financial Services | Ministry of Finance | Government of India](#))

Table no 5 shows financial Costs and Margins of RRBs from 2018–19 to 2023–24. The financial performance indicators of RRBs show a steady improvement in operational efficiency, cost management, and profitability over the six-year period.

Yield Performance: Yield on loans remained largely stable (8.8% to 8.87%), reflecting consistent lending returns within certain range despite changing interest rates. Yield on investments initially declined to 6.24% in 2021–22 but rose sharply to 7.39% in 2023–24, indicating improved returns from government securities and market-linked investments. Yield on assets shows a rising trend (7.5% to 7.76%), indicating enhanced overall earning efficiency.

Declining Cost Structure: Cost of deposits fell from 5% to 4.04% by 2022–23 before increasing slightly in 2023–24. This shows increased deposit mobilization at lower rates. The overall cost

of funds improved substantially (4.6% to 3.72% in 2021–22), but rose back to 4.2% in 2023–24, indicating some cost pressure in the recent year.

Cost Efficiency and Risk Profile: Staff cost remained moderate, peaking at 2.45% in 2021-22 and reducing to 1.94% in 2023–24—indicating better manpower restructuring post-amalgamation. Cost of management shows a downward trend from 3.6% to 2.69%, reflecting improved operational productivity and cost optimization. Risk cost reduced from 1.2% in 2018–19 to 0.82% by 2022–23, shows the improvement in asset quality and lower NPA. Thus, the financial data of RRBs shows strong financial revival with Improved yields and earning capacity, Lower cost of funds, Declining cost ratios, Reduced credit risk and sharp transformation from losses to consistent profitability.

Conclusion:

The study concludes that the amalgamation of Regional Rural Banks has significantly strengthened the rural banking system in India. The multi-phase consolidation process successfully tackled longstanding challenges related to inadequate capital, weak financial performance, and high NPAs. Although the number of RRBs declined drastically from 196 to 28, their branch network increased more than doubled, proving that consolidation enhanced outreach rather than shrinking it. Financial data from 2018–19 to 2023–24 clearly show substantial improvement in deposits, advances, investments, and reserves of RRBs. It shows enhanced public trust and stronger financial capability. Profitability improved remarkably, with the number of loss-making banks reducing from 19 to only 3, and profits rising at a CAGR of 37% during study period. The decline in GNPA and NNPA levels highlights better risk management, improved recovery rate, and increased borrower discipline after amalgamation. Operational productivity also increased due to cost optimization, risk management, and technological upgradation in RRBs.

Overall, the amalgamation policy succeeded in creating financially stronger, more efficient, and more competitive RRBs capable of fulfilling the need of rural India. However, continued reforms in digital banking, risk monitoring, staff training, and product diversification are essential to maintain the sustained growth of RRBs. The study affirms that the consolidation of RRBs has significantly improved their financial performance. As a result of this RRBs are in a better position to contribute to the economic development of rural areas.

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